

MODELLING OF LOW-FREQUENCY BROADBAND VIBRATION MITIGATION FOR A BAR EXPERIENCEING LONGITUDINAL VIBRATIONS USING DISTRIBUTED VIBRATION ABSORBERS.

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines a multifunctional composite metastructure designed to provide broadband vibration suppression without increasing the overall weight of the structure. The structure considered utilizes passive damping. The passive damping is achieved by the addition of vibration absorber inserts. Each insert is designed to absorb a specific frequency. Using multiple inserts in a single structure reduces the response for a range of frequencies. This is accomplished by examining a bar modelled as a series of discrete masses undergoing axial vibrations. Parameters such as the number of vibration absorbers and the natural frequencies of those absorbers are varied to investigate the feasibility of the proposed metastructures to mitigate the free response of structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The present work aims at creating structures with high damping without adding additional mass to the overall system. Instead of adding mass, the mass is redistributed in such a way that provides substantial vibration suppression. We begin the work by investigating discrete system models in the simplest case of unidirectional axial vibrations. The end goal is to be able to create a structure made completely of a stiff material (such as a metal or a polymer from a 3D printer) but is shaped in such a way that the damping is relatively high. This will be done through modifying the structure on a centimeter scale to create embedded spring-mass systems, which will be referred to as vibration absorber inserts. These vibration absorbers will be shaped in such a way that they represent a mass and a spring where the parameters can be tuned such that their natural frequency matches the fundamental natural frequency of the main structure. These types of structures are known as metastructures. Metastructures are a recent area of research derived from research in metamaterials which are simply defined as materials that are engineered materials built to exhibit properties not found in nature [1].

An example of this can be seen in Figure 1 which is from experiments performed by colleagues, Hobeck, Laurant and Inman and provides the physical parameters for the work presented here [2]. The structure shown was 3D printed using a stiff polymer. The structure is composed of the main structure and ten vibration absorber inserts distributed internally throughout. The smaller cubes represent the mass and the narrow bars represent the springs. Using the dimensions and material properties the effective mass and spring stiffness of the vibration absorbers (VAs) can be calculated. This example is solely provided to give the reader an idea of what a metastructure could look like. The results from Hobeck et al. experiments were performed to justify looking into the analytical models in greater detail. From their experiments, it can be seen that the structure behaves similarly to the discrete model presented in this paper. Their paper examines steady state vibration suppression while the work presented here is focused on controlling the free response [2].

Figure 1: Example of a 3D printed metastructure

The present work, aims at providing additional justification to continue looking into metastructure concepts and to show that there are benefits to using these types of inserts. This paper looks strictly at a discrete system undergoing axial vibrations. This is the best starting point because the analysis for a unidirectional discrete problem is relatively straight forward and enables understanding of the basic issues and phenomenon.

Much of this work builds off of work from two different fields, namely energy harvesting and tuned mass dampers. In order to harvest energy from vibrations, small mass-spring systems are placed at ideal locations such that they experience significant motion. Through piezoelectric materials this motion is then converted to electricity which can then be used to power small devices. Although the end goal is different, both energy harvesting and the work discussed here requires high levels of vibration in the spring-mass systems. Energy harvesting so that it can be converted to energy and vibration mitigation so that the energy is removed from the main structure. Thus the work done in energy harvesting can be extended to vibration absorbers and visa versa.

The civil engineering community relies heavily on tuned mass dampers to reduce the vibrations in larger structures such as skyscrapers and bridges [3]. Tuned mass dampers have the same end-goal as the distributed VAs presented here but the implementation is much different. The mass of the tuned mass dampers can be a significant portion of the total mass of the structure (up to 25% additional mass) which is reasonable to do for civil structures. This is referred to as add-on damping, since it is a solution that is simply added to the structure. In the case of aerospace structures, a large increase in the total mass and volume of the system is very expensive thus must be avoided. To fix this problem, small vibration absorbers are distributed throughout the structure and integrated with the main structure. These differences can be seen in Figure 2. Regardless of this difference, the end goal is the same. Information can be drawn for this field of work, especially looking at the methodology they use to choose the parameters of the tuned mass dampers to achieve the best performance. One significant difference between this work and that of tuned mass dampers, is that tuned mass dampers typically have added damping. The aim of this work is to create a structure out of a single stiff material, additional damping is not added.

Figure 2: Figures depicting the differences between (a) add-on damping and (b) distributed damping

2 ANALYTICAL MODEL

The present work focuses on a discretized bar model experiencing axial vibrations. Two different models will be utilized during the simulations, a baseline structure and a similar structure with vibration absorbers. These two structures have the same mass in order to create a useful comparison. These two structures can be seen in Figure 3. The baseline bar is discretized into n_m masses with springs connecting these masses in series. The structure with VAs is discretized into n_m discrete masses with one VA on each these masses (except for the far right mass) as shown in Figure 3b, such that the total number of VAs is n ($n = n_m - 1$). The larger masses are referred to as the main masses and the small masses as the VA masses; these masses are represented symbolically by m and m_i , respectively. The i refers to a specific mass on the structure and i ranges from 1 to n . The springs connecting the main masses are called the main springs and denoted k . A mass ratio, μ is defined for the structure with VAs as the ratio of mass in the VAs to the mass in the main masses given by

$$\mu = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n m_i}{n_m m} \quad (1)$$

For all simulations structural damping is utilized to approximate the total material damping in the structure. The damper at the root of the model is a simplified representation of distributed damping throughout the structure due to the polymer material.

(a) Baseline Structure

(b) Structure with Vibration Absorbers.

Figure 3: (a) The baseline bar model and (b) the tested bar model with distributed vibration absorbers

The results of the simulations show two plots, a frequency response function (FRF) and the time response do to an impulse. On each plot there are two lines a red dotted line for the baseline structure and a blue solid line for the structure with the VAs. The FRF is of the far right mass subjected to a force input on that same mass, $|X_{n+1}(s)/F_{n+1}(s)|$. The impulse response plot is the displacement time history of the same mass subjected to a forcing unit impulse at that same location.

Three different cases are examined in order to investigate the effect of changing a few different parameters. For the first two cases, the fundamental natural frequency of the baseline structure is calculated and all the VAs are tuned such that their natural frequency matches the fundamental natural frequency. The first case has two VAs and the second has 20 VAs. For the third case, instead of keeping all the frequencies of the VAs constant, they are varied in an attempt to get a more desirable result. For all the cases the same total mass was utilized and the main spring stiffnesses were chosen such that the fundamental natural frequencies of all the cases are approximately equal. The mass ratio used throughout is $\mu = 0.15$ and the total mass before and after the VAs are added remains the same.

2.1 Two Vibration Absorbers

To start a very simple model with only two VAs is examined. Much work has been done on a host structure with a single vibration absorber attached. In order to not replicate that work, here two vibration absorbers are examined [4, 5]. This leads to a total of five degrees of freedom. Using the model described above the mass, stiffness and damping matrices are assembled. From these matrices the FRF and impulse response can be easily calculated. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Results from simulation with two VAs all tuned to the same frequency

The fundamental peak of the original structure has split into two smaller peaks on either side of that frequency and the amplitude reduced. If the system was operating at strictly the fundamental frequency there would be good suppression but if the operating frequency is slightly off then the response would be high. If the time impulse time response of the system which excited a boarder band of frequencies is examined, the structure with the VAs overall has a slightly lower magnitude. It is unclear if this performance is much better than that of the baseline structure. Note from the time response in Figure 4 that the maximum amplitude resulting from an impulse reaches almost the same value for the case without the absorbers. This is because and impulse excites a broad band of frequencies and the absorption is only occurring at a single frequency.

2.2 Twenty Vibration Absorbers

For this next case, the degrees of freedom in the system are increased significantly. The numbers of main masses increases from three masses up to 21 masses. The main spring values k are chosen such that the fundamental natural frequency of the baseline system is similar to the case of two VAs. Again the total mass is the same for both the system with and without the absorbers, as before.

The results from this case look very similar to the two absorber case. Thus we find that changing the number of VAs in the structure does not do much if the VAs are all tuned to the same frequency.

Figure 5: Results from simulation with 20 VAs all tuned to the same frequency

2.3 Twenty Linearly Varying Vibration Absorbers

The idea behind this last model is to tune the VAs to a range of frequencies instead of a single frequency. This would hopefully create a bandgap and could also lower the magnitudes of the split peaks. The resonant peak for the baseline structure is at 532 Hz so in this case we vary the frequencies of the single VAs so they range from 350 Hz to 800 Hz in a linear manner. The mass of each vibration absorber is set from the definition of the mass ratio and the stiffness of the VAs springs varies according to the following relationship.

$$k_i = m_i \omega_n^2 \quad (2)$$

Figure 6: Results from simulation with 20 VAs with frequencies that linearly vary

The results from this case show significant improvement from the cases discussed before. The maximum amplitude of the FRF is significantly lower than in the previous case. The effect of this can be seen by looking at the impulse time response. The vibrations die out much more quickly than in the baseline case. It is interesting to note the beating phenomenon that occurs around the 0.05 second mark. This is due to the change in frequency from one vibration absorber to the next. Since the frequencies are close, they constructively and destructively interfere to create the beats. The difference in the frequencies can be related to the beat period by $T_{beat} = 1/\Delta f$ and this beat period corresponds to the period seen on the figure.

3 CONCLUSIONS

From the work presented here, it is clear that working with these types of structures has potential to provide substantial vibration suppression without greatly increasing the mass of the overall structure. In the last case shown, the time response of the structure has been greatly reduced. Thus using the distributed vibration absorbers provides greater flexibility in tuning the parameters of the system to get a desirable response. The most important finding is that this can be done without adding mass to the system. The varying of frequencies of the inserts does lead to beating phenomenon in the impulse response, but at very low amplitude. The impacts of this phenomenon must be evaluated before implementing it into a specific application. The work presented here sets up the opportunity for future work optimizing the various parameters, adding nonlinearity, consideration of multidimensional and the inclusion of smart materials to perform sensing, actuation and control.

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